

CULTUROLOGY

THE ROLE OF LIBRARIES OF TEMPORARILY DISPLACED UNIVERSITIES IN ENSURING THE SUSTAINABILITY AND ACCESSIBILITY OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN WARTIME

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Abstract

In conditions of criminal aggression and forced relocation of higher education institutions, the issue of maintaining the continuity of the educational process and access to educational and scientific resources becomes critically important, as providing students with the necessary knowledge is a guarantee of their future professional success. Libraries of temporarily displaced universities are key centres of information support, providing students, teachers and researchers with the necessary materials regardless of geographical or infrastructural constraints. The use of modern information and communication technologies, the development of electronic resources and the adaptation of services to distance and blended learning formats are becoming the basis for the sustainability and resilience of the educational environment. At the same time, libraries perform an important function of preserving academic heritage and maintaining scientific communication, which contributes to the integration and adaptation of displaced universities into the national and international scientific and educational space. In the context of military challenges, their activities combine traditional forms of library service with innovative approaches aimed at ensuring equal access to knowledge and resources. Thus, libraries are becoming not only an infrastructural or exclusively scientific, but also a strategic link in preserving the integrity and quality of the educational process in crisis conditions.

Keywords: scientific libraries of higher education institutions, internally displaced higher education institutions, adaptation strategies, support for the educational process.

Analysis of research and publications. Along with the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation, the issue of studying the resilience and sustainability of the activities of higher education institution libraries has gained relevance; thus, the study by I. I. Stambol [6] describes the activities of libraries in the city of Odesa during the first months of the invasion. The article by S. Ivanenko [1] analyzes the work of the Scientific Library of the E. O. Paton Institute of Electric Welding of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, highlighting changes in the approaches and areas of activity of a rather narrowly specialized institution. The issue of preservation and development of libraries is also raised by O. Vasylenko [7]. The problem of adapting the system of functions of Ukrainian libraries under martial law is covered by L. Kravets [4]. Such systematic work of many researchers indicates considerable interest in preserving the functioning of library institutions themselves, as well as the further need for thorough scientific research.

The relevance of the study is based on the need to highlight the means and ways of integrating libraries of higher education institutions into the realities of the present. It also helps to highlight the transformations taking place in the services provided by libraries, their creation of new technological, organizational, and educational models, which, in turn, highlights comprehensive approaches to ensuring the resilience and sustainability of the educational process within higher education institutions themselves.

Presentation of the main material. We agree with the opinion of O. Klymenko and N. Bachynska [3] that it is precisely “reader-centrism” that is the main

guarantee of the success of a modern library’s activity, while the “accumulation of collections” gradually assumes a secondary function, since the priority becomes not only the preservation and replenishment of printed and electronic resources, but also ensuring their maximum accessibility and relevance to the needs of users (readers). In modern conditions, the library acts not so much as a repository of knowledge, but rather as an active communicative and service space capable of promptly responding to the requests of the academic community. For the libraries of universities that were forced to leave the premises of their own higher education institutions, such user orientation acquires particular significance, since it is precisely the individualization of communication approaches, such as active involvement in the development of their own social networks (Facebook, Instagram), the development of remote services, and the integration of digital resources, that make it possible to maintain the continuity of the educational process. Thus, the concept of “reader-centrism” [3] is transformed into the strategic foundation of the library’s activity, determining its adaptability, innovativeness, and ability to function effectively under conditions of wartime challenges and limited resources.

On May 16, 2025, on the basis of the temporarily displaced higher education institution Kherson State University, which at that time was located at Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, an All-Ukrainian seminar was held with the aim of uniting the libraries of temporarily displaced universities under the common slogan: “New challenges – new opportunities” [5], which, in our opinion, demonstrates the scientific

community's aspiration to consolidate efforts, its inclination toward cooperation, and its ability to develop strategies for responding to crisis circumstances and to form a unified vision for the development of library services in new socio-cultural and technological realities.

In our further research, we use the seminar materials as a source for the practical analysis of various approaches to adaptation and support of the scientific and educational process in the above-mentioned higher education institutions.

As representatives of the KSU library indicate, their transformational path was forced; however, it was precisely this circumstance that provided the impetus for strategic changes. During the period of forced displacement, library staff have regularly conducted seminars for Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) candidates on the topic "Scientometrics in the Life of a Researcher," highlighting the importance of mastering scientometric skills as an integral part of a young scholar's work. Such events contribute to the development of skills in effective search, analysis, and interpretation of scientific information, increasing publication activity and the academic visibility of researchers. They are also aimed at raising awareness among young scholars, particularly within the framework of academic integrity.

It is precisely in the context of academic integrity that in 2024 the library staff organized a round table: "Open Science and the Role of the Library in Supporting Scientific Research" [2], which was attended not only by master's students but also by representatives of scientific libraries of other higher education institutions, namely: H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University, etc. The event became a kind of platform for discussing modern approaches to implementing the principles of integrity, increasing the level of transparency and accessibility of research results, as well as for exchanging best practices among libraries of different higher education institutions. Particular attention was paid to the role of the library as an intermediary between researchers and global information resources, capable of providing not only access to scientific data but also methodological support for research activities, which, in our opinion, rightly correlates with the principles of the above-mentioned "reader-centeredness."

It is also worth emphasizing that the library staff hold meetings with first-level higher education students aimed at familiarizing new students with the work of the library, already in a virtual format, since, unfortunately, all the buildings of Kherson State University were damaged.

Particular attention was paid to institutions of the so-called "first wave" [5], that is, higher education institutions from the temporarily occupied territories of Donetsk region, Luhansk region, and Crimea.

A representative of Luhansk Taras Shevchenko National University, Ms. Mariia Pochynkova, delivered a presentation entitled: "The Library of a Displaced University: Losses, Prospects, Opportunities." It is worth emphasizing that a "School of Academic Integrity" was established on the basis of the library, in which, as of 2024, 738 faculty members and students

have completed training. This became a vivid example of the systematic work of the library in the direction of forming a culture of academic integrity among academic and pedagogical staff and students, and the scale of coverage indicates the success of the chosen model for implementing the educational program, and a high level of engagement in such initiatives.

Despite the absence of an automated library and information system (only the software "UFD Library" remained partially accessible, as well as the absence of professionally trained staff, and significant physical losses of collections), during the second displacement the LNU library gained access to new automated software Koha, which made it possible to significantly increase the level of staff qualification.

This implementation became not only a technical update but also a factor in the qualitative transformation of all library activities, as it allowed for the creation of a "multi-location library," given that the university is forced to operate simultaneously in three cities of the Poltava region. The transition to the Koha platform opened up opportunities for the systematization of collections, the expansion of search tools, and an increase in reader service efficiency, particularly through integration with electronic catalogs and external databases, with which the LNU library is steadily expanding its cooperation. Simultaneously with the technical changes, the process of increasing digital literacy and professional competencies of employees began, which made it possible to compensate for personnel losses—as only two employees without specialized higher education remained during the second relocation (from Starobilsk to the Poltava region)—and to create conditions for the implementation of innovative services. Thus, gaining access to Koha became an important stage in overcoming the consequences of material and personnel losses, and also made it possible to form a new library model oriented toward flexibility, interactivity, and the continuous renewal of services in the interests of the academic community.

The LNU Library identifies opportunities for further development in deepening the use of digital capabilities, specifically strengthening the already high rankings of its own repository, as well as expanding the integration of the repository with international scientometric databases and open access platforms. One of the priority areas is the development of analytical tools for monitoring the use and citation of scholarly works, which will contribute to increasing the visibility of the university's research results in the global scientific community.

Representatives of the Dmytro Motomyi Tavsia State Agrotechnological University, which was previously based in Melitopol and is now located in Zaporizhzhia at the Zaporizhzhia National University, also joined the discussion.

To support the educational process, library staff created "Thematic Collections" that meet the requirements of the university's educational programs and cover the main disciplinary areas of student training. The formation of these "Thematic Collections" is carried out manually by library staff, taking into account

curriculum plans and programs, which ensures their relevance and practical value for students and teachers. The collections themselves include periodicals and academic manuals in digital format, as almost the entire library collection was lost in the temporarily occupied territories.

Separately, an index was created according to the Sustainable Development Goals, providing quick access to literature covering issues of ecology, sustainable growth, innovation, and partnership.

Among the informational and educational activities, it is worth highlighting the large number of events aimed both at patriotic education, such as “Ukraine. The Strength of an Unconquered Nation”, “Capitals of Ukraine: A Journey Through History”, and purely professional ones (related to the university’s agricultural specialization): “Dmytro Motoronyi. A Pioneer of the Agricultural Sector”. Such student engagement allows the library to transform not only as a scientific resource but also as a center of the university’s cultural life, contributing to the preservation of the institution’s “distinctive feature” [5]. As a consequence of the full-scale invasion by the Russian Federation, the staff faced the challenge not only of preserving national memory and regional achievements but also of addressing past mistakes [5].

Conclusions. Analyzing the activities of libraries of internally displaced higher education institutions, based only on several examples: KSU, Taras Shevchenko LNU, and TDATU, we confirmed the previously stated view that the library has become a catalyst for transformations in the educational and scientific process. Despite the inevitability of the transformations themselves, the loss of paper collections, loss of staff, destruction of buildings, and, in our opinion, the most painful – the loss of personnel, libraries demonstrate high adaptability and integration into scientific and educational activities. The conduct of online events and training courses aimed at enhancing academic integrity and transparency of the educational process itself also indicates readiness to respond to the needs of students and academic staff.

Digital innovations are also of particular importance, such as digitization of collections, continuous

expansion of the repository, and implementation of specialized, advanced library and information systems (Koha, etc.).

In our work, we focused on only some of the libraries of displaced higher education institutions; as of now, according to the report of the Ministry of Education of Ukraine, there are 44 such institutions [2], which makes further scientific research in the area we have defined even more relevant.

References

1. Ivanenko, S. (2023). Main directions of activity of the library of a scientific institution of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine in the conditions of martial law. *Naukovi pratsi Natsionalnoi biblioteky Ukrainy imeni V. I. Vernadskoho*, (68), 125–138.
2. Kherson State University. (2025). Round table on open science and the role of the library in supporting scientific research was held at KSU. URL: <https://www.kspu.edu/PublisherReader.aspx?newsId=20041&lang=uk> (Accessed: 06 August 2025).
3. Klymenko, O., & Bachynska, N. (2011). Main directions of activity of university libraries of the Ministry of Culture of Ukraine at the present stage. *Bibliotechnyi Visnyk*, (4), 38–45.
4. Kravets, L. (2023). Adaptation of the system of functions of Ukrainian libraries in the conditions of martial law. *Naukovi pratsi Natsionalnoi biblioteky Ukrainy imeni V. I. Vernadskoho*, (68), 150–159.
5. Marchenko, I. O. (2025). All-Ukrainian seminar “Libraries of displaced universities: new challenges – new opportunities” [Video]. *YouTube*. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1a1qiltnGWk> (Accessed: 07 August 2025).
6. Stambol, I. I. (2022). Features of the activity of Odesa libraries during the martial law of 2022. *Visnyk Kharkivskoho natsionalnoho universytetu imeni V. N. Karazina. Seriya “Istoriia”*, (62), 128–141.
7. Vasylenko, O., & Demianiuk, L. (2023). Preservation and innovative development of libraries in modern conditions. *Bibliotechnyi Visnyk*, (4), 80–86.